

MESS 0011

Utilizing the ORDA:INED standard¹; American Integrated Circuit is a company built around STEMM utilizing Operations Research and Data

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ABSTRACT

American Integrated Circuit is a startup in response to a post COVID/post 2020 supply & logistics world. Particularly in the wake of issues surrounding the USA vs. China-Russia or Allies vs. New Axis powers *shi* or geopolitical disposition. It was birthed from necessity, and this fuels its needs to use every leverage. For that matter, nothing will provide this advancement as strongly as the superb IP and opportunity, and of course the ORDAINED standard - a MIMS/MESSy product by the COO/author.

Keywords: business - semiconductors -silicon - growth - Starter Grower - Power Curve

¹ Above: Figure 1; see: MESS0007

https://www.academia.edu/87578071/MESS0007_MIMS_2_101_The_ORDA_Standard

American Integrated Circuit is a SPACERStm and AIMtm certified company

SPACERS² is typified by:

- A movement of humankind towards conquering the solar system, and eventually becoming an interstellar and perhaps even intergalactic civilization; as opposed to self-destructing because of catastrophism scars and a cultural DNA version of PTSD.
- A standard of items to focus on, based upon an EPEMC framework of cosmogony, that emphasizes:
 - **STEMM**
 - **Power**
 - **Analytics**
 - **Cryptologics**
 - **Electrical Energetics** (and economics - particularly Dual Layer Economics)
 - **Research** (and resilience, as in FREETH)
 - **Strategy** (and shi)

AIM³ is typified by:

- Scalability
 - hence the purchase and control of a 6,000,000 sq. ft. facility to be secured underground.
- Repeatability
- Scriptability

From its inception, AIC - americanintegratedcircuit.com - has been built to be scaled up, rapidly, automated, and involved in the power and electrical space. It takes into account the strategy issues, as well as being designed heavily around science, engineering, and even medicine. The final aspects of analytics and cryptologics - in this case cryptocurrency tokens for the sake of *utility* as well as raising investment - are discussed in this very foundational document.

AIC is an ORDAINED company

“God bless America” is a common phrase, and these days, many are providing lip service to the idea, but doing little to make sure God *continues* to bless the US of A! At American Integrated Circuit, the initial framework is built around an America which can be relied upon again:

- Built by Americans
- Employs Americans
- For American or American led infrastructure
- Defenders of the West
- Capable of exporting to the world
- Establishes the New American Executive
- Trains top leaders and provides top tier advisement and consulting to the private and government sectors.

More to the point of this document, the corporation is built with OR/DA in mind:

- ❖ Operations

² <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/spacers>

³ <https://bit.ly/3oezRhD>

- The author acts as Chief Operating Officer, ensuring that the company has a strong start with a direct foundation on OR/DA. Did UPS or Intel or Dell Corp have this advantage? Not at all. All the more leverage for AIC to achieve the \$65B valuation heights.
- ❖ Research
 - The company's IP represents a new form of production of SiC and SiCl₄ and only the start of production of many new items. The CEO, Aaron Hardin, has been planning out this scalable IP for years. But when his own company - Hardin Scientific⁴ - was affected directly by the asymmetric New Cold War⁵, in the form of raised chip prices, he didn't sit back and do nothing. *He acted.* And he doesn't stop researching at any moment for the paths of least resistance.
- ❖ Data
 - The company gathers data utilizing the ZOHO cloud.
- ❖ Analytics
 - The author and COO, works with the CEO to design and implement new forms of analytics using AI and ZOHO software.
- ❖ Implementation
 - The application of ORDA from the ground up, through the ZOHO - and later the QLE™ system - will lead to the perfection of the manufacturing and supply/logistics processes.
- ❖ Numericalization
 - The COO's emphasis upon KPI's, and financial efficiency, as well as strict inventory and sales - the entire process - will enable the CEO to scale the company as rapidly as possible.
- ❖ Efficiency
 - The IP has been pre-engineered using Miro software.
 - The sales process has been designed using GERU software.
- ❖ Definition
 - The clarity of the data will be maintained by strict control under the eyes of CTO Justin Taylor and VP of Engineering, Jonathan Kines.
 - Financial controls will be under the strict control of the Chairman of the Board, the CFO (and Treasurer), and COO. However, the COO will insist upon a Next^{Next} level of cost and quality control, part by part, chemical drop by chemical drop, to determine all the bottlenecks and chokepoints to a degree not seen outside the Six Sigma/Black Belt heights of Toyota!

AIC+AIM leads to a FREETH^E standard: the use of Eulium will change the industrial and business landscape

- ❖ Freedom
- ❖ Resilience
- ❖ Equality
- ❖ Energy Economy
- ❖ Tough-Minded
- ❖ Humanist
- ❖ Eulium.org⁶

⁴ www.hardinscientific.com

⁵ https://www.academia.edu/51022722/Winning_the_New_Cold_War_World_War_3

⁶ Cryptocurrency which uses *Proof of Power* www.eulium.org/wp.pdf or <https://bit.ly/3UTMY7V>

The R&D department or budget of AIC will enable the rapid growth in several key initiatives, helping reduce the EPEMC and SPACERS Project Power Curves⁷, significantly. By combining the traditional FREETH score and algorithm (co: the author) with A. Hardin's Eulium project (and Proof of Power), the score will birth a new manner of utilizing NFTs to rapidly certify business documentation⁸. While simultaneously enabling both scientific and corporate fundraising.

AIC lays the foundations for the SPACERS future

In order to accomplish the calculations for the Birkeland Polyphase Superweb⁹, and the satellite expansion, the author is recommending a 1×10^{21} increase in computational power via networked, edge or cloud computing and connectivity. To do this, there must be a concordant increase in the volume of computational chips. Where do the resources come from? From AIC, because it is located in Kentucky, where massive quartz and sand resources reside. With the highways criss-crossing the state, it is also ideal for delivery south to the Carolinas, and north to the new Intel facility in Ohio.

Getting Humanity past Phase 1 of Stage 1¹⁰

The current powers that be want to eliminate American strength, and establish their power in space. China, in particular, wishes to establish its centralized power in space with a 1km long space cruiser¹¹, and is using lasers to attack the US and NATO satellite grid. The N.W.O. (perhaps the E.U. and World Bank, and other NGOs like the World Economic Forum) want to dethrone the US, remove property and other property rights. They have a clear bent towards neo-feudal oligarchy, and wish to hamper the US Dollar. This cannot be allowed to happen. Therefore AIC will lead the way in both OR/DA and in FREETH to "free the US" and free the People. Not with bombs and guns, but by building the New America.

From there, entirely new cities¹² will be built around the need to get mankind from Stage 1 to Stage 2.¹³ This process will force mankind out of the doldrums of Phase 1, which is characterized by rockets and limitations of energy systems. All new True Green Energy systems, and deep mining operations, robots, automation, AI, etc. will require (at present, under this technological paradigm) microchips and other semiconductor related products. This growth cannot be met by the present production rates, even at present growth trends (10x in 7 years), let alone with megalopolis and spacebase, and ultra deep space mining in our Phase 2 future. Phase 2 of SPACERism and conquering the solar system will be all about super scaled up volume of very scaled down microchips for microcontrollers, interconnected systems and sensors, and supercomputing. Multibeam technology will be the minimum stat level for playing in this field, and no other "big

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https://www.academia.edu/87225337/MESS0002_MIMS_2_11_1_EPEMC_Management_As_Applied_through_the_Project_Power_Curve

⁸ Non-fungible Token; through the stamp of an image of stock, certificates, or a QR to a document, the eulium blockchain can track transactions exactly

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https://www.academia.edu/38560727/Birkeland_Polyphase_Superweb_A_Proposition_for_the_Future_Betterment_of_Mankind_global_defense_interconnection_and_unlimited_power

¹⁰ And avoiding a Moonbase Hegemony (Elysium) from the NWO, CCP, or alien-elite (if they exist)

¹¹ <https://www.thetimes.co.uk/article/china-unveils-plan-for-huge-space-station-78f88x9mv>

¹² https://www.academia.edu/62757621/Conquering_the_Solar_System pp.28-29

¹³ Moonbase → Terraforming Mars

boy” or “blue chip” semiconductor company is thinking at our level of scale. \$65B is just the start. AIC will carry into the future, and into the \$\$ quadrillions in valuation.

AIC+Resilient Way builds the New American Executive

Tough-Minded Management, and Executiveship is not only about American style ‘rigged individualism’, it is about *design*. We at AIC will design the new Executive. Chips that control wearable tech, and designing Web 4.0, as well as decentralized and secure communications and up-to-the-nanosecond updated data and information. Also, top tier management and leadership training programs, and working with the best, in a corporate culture that is far less gouache and “silicon valley” (which has fallen out of favor and touch with the Real America), and far more rugged Appalachian. It is not the tech geeks that will represent the America of the future, but the new supermen and superwomen, carried by AIC and Hardin Scientific related technology. Their secure comms are protected by blockchain encryption, and computed on AIC server farms, located in secure facilities running on massive fiber bundles. The power use, of course, mediated by TGE approaches.

AIC is Built to Grow and Provide a MIMS Creation Area (MIMSCA)

The corporate environment is also meant for scale. Less toxicity, less fascism, less fear of reprisal, and less political hampering and grandstanding than the Big Tech/Data that the FAANG offers now. Their hijacking of the Web 3.0 after ruining Web 2.0 is going to be countermanded by the Web 4.0 approach of the author¹⁴ and CEO, working together on the AIM requirements.

Eulium → Business Development

Eulium token will bring proof of stake of the ETH blockchain together with proof of work to perform useful transactions, in the creation of the world’s first “proof of power” standard. By helping companies and scientists and inventors raise capital for future investment, the Eulium blockchain will lead to a slew of utility-based crypto “currencies” that change mankind’s computational future *for the better*. Less fascism, more freedom, and more responsibility.

QLE™ Enterprise Management System

The author’s Quantum Leap Engine will be funded and grown by first finishing the Starter Grower MIMS (www.startergrower.com) and creating the world’s best free online business evaluation tool for business owners and consultants. From there the full Web2.0 backbone will be grown, with a full scale OR/DA and AI plan, to take QLE into the future, and revolutionize the business marketplace, literally.

Figure 3 - Present PPC and Resilient Score

¹⁴ Ibid. pp. 65-66

STEMM Arena

The CEO's vision is not all about money. He has an educational project ready to launch, as soon as we can reach the 500m valuation (goal: 2025), leading to the renovation of the materialist America and the dying mini-mall infrastructure... repurposed for the growth of science, technology, engineering, mathematics, and medicine education, as well as labs for kids and young entrepreneurs. Think "Hacksmith"¹⁵, without the overhead to hamper them.

Solar, VAWT, Water, and Stirling Engine Power Systems

The company will utilize state-of-the-art solar photovoltaics, eventually manufactured by the company's own chip manufacture, to power itself with the PACE program¹⁶. However, that isn't a True Green Energy¹⁷. As such the CEO and COO are planning for systems to utilize the land of the property for full water and wind technological systems, as well as development of the world's first mega-geothermal Stirling Engine designs.

Monolith Power Project

The R&D department will begin work on the author's Monolith Power system, and spin-off a company for the utilization of this IP, creating an instant demand for both AIC chips and Hardin Scientific microcontroller Hardware-as-a-Service design. The communications of these will be on the Eulium blockchain, and profits derived will go into further TGE development, as well as a team of over 100 top programmers dedicated to the production of the Web 4.0 standards. For Web 4.0 to exist, AIC will push microchip tech design into the next level of engineering, both upper limits and smaller limits of size through the use of multibeam technologies.

QiRI + Hardin Scientific

With the scale control, and ceasing reliance upon TSMC¹⁸ technologies, AIC will enable Hardin Scientific to dominate the HaaS market for private and government sectors. But the R&D department will help the author develop the secretive QiRI project¹⁹ (this is a codename). Suffice it to say, the revolutionary potential for the medical space for either project is **immense**.

References

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¹⁶ <https://www.energy.gov/eere/slsc/property-assessed-clean-energy-programs>

¹⁷ Ibid. pp.17-22

¹⁸ <https://www.tsmc.com/english>

¹⁹ <https://www.researchgate.net/project/Clinical-Electric-Field-Treatments-and-Measurements-QiRI>